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Youth
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YOUTH EMPOWERMENT THROUGH ENTREPRENEURSHIP:

*The 21st Century Need for Sustained
Economic Development.*

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Youth empowerment and entrepreneurship development as its basic component have become household terms in Nigeria and other subjects in the world today. These have derived from the events of the global economic downturn which have driven many nations of the world towards deepening entrepreneurship and generic (soft) skills in the citizens, who are mostly youths and therefore, believably seen as the most potent tool for achieving the needed self-dependence, poverty reduction and economic empowerment.

In Nigeria, the situation is not different. The few Government jobs for potential graduates and the large number of unemployed youths have become a strong force acting on government and other stake holding agencies to get all citizens economically empowered through the programme of entrepreneurship. Youth empowerment is a clear root to poverty reduction and could lead to general development in our nation. Empowering the youth helps bring them into the mainstream of the development process. Youth empowerment involves getting the youths to carefully manage the available resources around them; giving them the enablement, authority and control over their own life situation in economic, political and social independence. Economically, when youths are empowered, the focus is on poverty alleviation and attainment of sustainable livelihood by helping them to enhance their entrepreneurial skills, creating enhanced access to credit and market information and reforming policies that hinder the realization of their full potentials.

The World Bank as far back as 2001 had identified entrepreneurship as an empowering tool and that through skills acquisition as its vital component, unemployment and poverty are significantly reduced particularly, as it seeks to provide participants with the capability and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of settings. Entrepreneurial training or education has been variously defined by different authors. Consortium for Entrepreneurship Education in 2004, defined it as education that seeks to prepare people, especially, the youths to be responsible enterprising individuals who become entrepreneurs and entrepreneurial thinkers and contribute to economic development and sustained Communities.

In a school setting, entrepreneurship education is a cross disciplinary area with contributions from a variety of specialists including technical, vocational, natural/social sciences, mathematics, communications (language) and other disciplines. In other

In other settings outside school, many vocations or tasks such as hair dressing/ haircut, catering, fashion and graphic designs, photography, poultry, fishery, make up artistry among others, are areas of life where entrepreneurial skills are urgently required for the youths to excel.

It is in consideration of the importance of entrepreneurship education in encouraging skills acquisition in human capacity building, and particularly as a means for reducing chronic unemployment and poverty that the National Universities Commissions (NUC) in 2004 recommended that Nigerian Universities, Polytechnics and Colleges of Education integrate skills acquisition through this education as an integral part of the curriculum after the pattern of the USA Business Schools. It has since been made a compulsory course for all undergraduates in different areas of specialization. In support of this, a renown Professor, and an International Education Strategist, Pai Obanya has summarized the role of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria to be one conceived of, as a vehicle for realizing the National goal of acquiring appropriate attitudes, values, knowledge and skills for the development of mental, physical and social abilities which an individual needs to live and contribute maximally to the development of the society. The question every observer of our economy seems to ask today, however, is, if our education has laid this sound foundation for entrepreneurs to be self-actualized youths and which should contribute to transformational change in society, why is the major challenge facing the youth today still hinging on how to get the youths to be gainfully employed? This is the very reason individuals, organizations and governments are beckoning on youths and other citizens to avail themselves of vast opportunities existing everywhere including the internet to learn and acquire entrepreneurship skills for self-productive living. The quest is made to all youths who can create or be enabled to create value by offering a product or service; can have a strong believe about a market opportunity and accordingly organize very little resources at their disposal effectively to accomplish outcome, such already have their lives half-way transformed.

The skills enhanced or acquired through entrepreneurship/empowerment programmes will no doubt equip individual youths to eventually engage in vocations with the ability to lead new creation, exhibit creative mind, self-reliance, innovation, risk taking ability initiatives, team spirit, resourcefulness, financial control, self-confidence, versatility, originality, knowledgeable, dynamic thinking, optimum disposition, people oriented flexibility in decision, energy for hard work, responses to suggestions and criticisms, driven by need achievement, profit-oriented, persistent and preserving, adjustment to challenges and future looking for the purpose of leading self-reliant lives.

A society having youths loaded with such skills and are determined to venture into relevant businesses (mostly their own) will obviously put an end to the search for non existence public employment which has for a long time complicated the problem of unemployment in Nigeria with detestable and menacing consequences. The increased lack of job opportunities particularly in the

public sector has lengthened the period of youths' dependence on parents and guardians for their livelihoods; increased poverty and consequent poor standard of living with attendant consequences as youth restiveness, gangsterism, political thuggery, cultism, deep feeling of frustration and hopelessness due to indebtedness, murder, suicide and loss of property among others. Burdened by these ills, the various governments; Federal and International, have further introduced various programmes aimed at wealth creation to reduce poverty. Federal Government of Nigeria through various youth development initiatives such as Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Programme (SURE-P), National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP), National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDs), National Directorate of Empowerment (NDE), The Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRI) among numerous others, is still making concerted efforts to ensure that the youths lead productive and self-reliant lives in order to counter the evidently shrinking labour market system.

It is hoped that the recent Federal Empowerment Programme, N-Power project in which 500, 000 unemployed Nigerian are targeted for gainful employment in the N-Teach, N-Health and N-Agro as well as in other sub-sectors like Building and Construction, will not be nailed like others by corruption and other ills in the Nigerian society. Government and other youths empowerment sponsoring agencies including well-meaning individuals need to gear efforts towards creating adequate financial support for the youths that have accepted to train as entrepreneurs. It is important to note that the breeding ground for our future entrepreneurs are medium and small scale enterprises and these should therefore, be encouraged.

The essence of youth empowerment especially in acquiring entrepreneurship training is to engage them meaningfully and enable them make a living out of the work they do. Idemudia, a onetime anchor of a Sunday programme called "Hotel De-Jordan" which ran on Bendel Television in the 1990s often said that "it is the work you learn that will feed you in your lifetime". This in essence implies that the potential youth entrepreneur that is unemployed today but who adheres to the above, will be fed and remain self reliant in a period of economic recession. However, those that neglect the clarion call for skill training and other empowerment will search endlessly for the unavailable jobs. Indeed, the global focus of employment and wealth creation is the continued development of the small and medium enterprise sector (SMEs).

In conclusion, the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills and the encouragement by various individuals, agencies and governments remain a potent means of encouraging youth employment and productive self-dependence. It is however, recommended that youths seeking skills, financial and other empowerment be encouraged to do so with all amount of discipline and determination and in addition seek relevance in the use of internet in order to be able to access most of the portals (websites) of empowering agencies.